

Sir David Cox's Statistical Philosophy and its Relevance to Today's Statistical Controversies

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Abstract

I discuss Sir David Cox's views of the nature and importance of statistical foundations and their relevance to today's controversies about statistical inference, particularly in using statistical significance tests. A central theme in Cox's statistical philosophy is the importance of calibrating methods by considering their behavior in (actual or hypothetical) repeated sampling. Two key questions are open to philosophical controversy:

How can the frequentist calibration be used as an evidential or inferential assessment?

How can we ensure that the hypothetical long-run used in calibration is relevant to the specific data?

I will discuss the answers that emerge from Cox's work and our jointly written papers, Mayo and Cox (2006) and Cox and Mayo (2010) on statistical significance testing, objectivity in statistics, and conditioning.

Key Words: calibration, conditioning, Sir David R. Cox, statistical foundations, statistical philosophy, statistical significance tests

1. Introduction

Sir David Cox who, sadly, passed away on January 18, 2022, is well known for his pioneering work, which has transformed applied statistics and for which he has received the top awards in the field of statistics.¹ Less well known is the importance he placed on matters of statistical foundations and his interest in the philosophy of statistics. Throughout his work, Cox laid out the seminal ideas and key points of controversy that comprise the core of statistical foundations. In a 1978 paper, he writes "the aims of a study of foundations include":

- (i) qualitative clarification of the objectives of statistical work;
- (ii) formal justification of, or even improvements to, procedures of analysis...
- (iii) the provision of a systematic basis for tackling new problems. (44)

In the preface to his 2006, *Principles of Statistical Inference*, he explains:

Without some systematic structure statistical methods for the analysis of data become a collection of tricks that are hard to assimilate and interrelate to one another. ...The development of new methods appropriate for new problems would become entirely a matter of ad hoc ingenuity. ...[O]ne role of theory is to assimilate, generalize and perhaps modify and improve the fruits of such ingenuity.

¹ Some of Sir David Cox's honors and awards are: Guy Medal (Silver, 1961) (Gold, 1973); Kettering Prize and Gold Medal for Cancer Research for the development of the Proportional Hazard Regression Model (1990); Knighted by Queen Elizabeth II (1985); George Box Medal (2005); Copley Medal (2010); International Prize in Statistics (2016). See "Remembering Sir David Cox: 1924-2022", in *Significance*: Firth, Reid, Mayo, Battey (2022).

Much of the theory is concerned with ... assessing the relative merits of different methods of analysis, and it is important even at a very applied level to have some understanding of the strengths and limitations of such discussions. This is connected with somewhat more philosophical issues connected with the nature of probability. A final reason, and a very good one, for study of the theory is that it is interesting. (xiii)

The goal of this paper is to discuss central elements of David Cox's statistical philosophy in relation to today's statistical controversies, especially regarding statistical significance testing. I had the good fortune to talk and work directly with Cox on these issues beginning the summer of 2003.

1.1 Our Collaboration

How does a philosopher of statistics wind up working with a giant in statistics? It was late summer of 2003 when I (boldly) invited Cox to be in a session I was forming on philosophy of statistics for the Second Erich L. Lehmann Symposium, (May 19–22, 2004; Rice University, Texas). I was surprised when he said yes. For one thing, it was in the U.S. and he was at Oxford. For another, Erich Lehmann, in whose honor the symposium was named, had been a prominent student of Jerzy Neyman and had developed statistical significance testing in the tradition of Neyman's decision-theoretical approach.² In contrast, Cox was aligned with the more inferential perspective championed by Ronald A. Fisher. Lastly, the session focused on philosophical issues, not typically at the forefront of statistical conferences.

For the next two years Cox and I talked about how to view "frequentist statistics as a theory of inductive inference", which became a joint paper with that title in the conference proceedings (Mayo and Cox 2006). The following few years resulted in a second paper, "Objectivity and Conditionality in Frequentist Inference" (Cox and Mayo 2010).³ My discussion will revolve around these two papers:

[1] "Frequentist Statistics as a Theory of Inductive Inference" (Mayo and Cox 2006).

[2] "Objectivity and Conditionality in Frequentist Inference" (Cox and Mayo 2010).

Our discussions were a blend of statistics and philosophy of science. In an informal published discussion (Cox and Mayo 2011), we had this exchange:

Cox: [I]n some fields foundations do not seem very important, but we both think that foundations of statistical inference are important; why do you think that is?

Mayo: I think because they ask about fundamental questions of evidence, inference, and probability ... we invariably cross into philosophical questions about empirical knowledge and inductive inference. (Cox and Mayo 2011, 103)

Some even regard statistics as a kind of "applied philosophy of science" (Fisher 1935a,b; Kempthorne 1976), and statistical theory as "applied philosophy of inductive inference". A core question that permeates inductive philosophy both in statistics and philosophy is: What is the nature and role of probabilistic concepts, methods, and models in making inferences in the face of limited data, uncertainty, and error?

1.2 Calibration: Weak Repeated Sampling Principle

A central theme in Cox's statistical philosophy is the importance of calibrating methods, that is, considering how they would behave in (actual or hypothetical) repeated sampling. In his view "it

² For discussions of the historical development, see Cox (2006) and Lehmann (2011).

³ In June 2006, Cox presented the joint work from [1] at a conference I organised at Virginia Tech, ERROR 06. A 2010 workshop ("Statistical Science and Philosophy of Science: Where Do/Should They Meet?") at the London School of Economics and Political Science links to [2].

seems clear that any proposed method of analysis that in repeated application would mostly give misleading answers is fatally flawed” (Cox 2006, 198). Cox dubbed this the *Weak Repeated Sampling Principle*. In the context of statistical significance tests, Cox and Hinkley (1974) defined it this way: “[W]e should not follow procedures which for some possible parameter values would give, in hypothetical repetitions, misleading conclusions most of the time” (45–6). Fifty percent gives a very minimal threshold.

1.3 Calibration: Two Foundational Questions

Two questions that arise remain open to philosophical controversy:

- How can the frequentist calibration be used as an evidential or inferential assessment (epistemological use)?
- How can we ensure: “that the hypothetical long run used in calibration is relevant to the specific data” (Cox 2006, 198)?

The first question leads to philosophical issues for a frequentist because it is generally thought that the best, if not the only, way to use probability for an epistemological assessment is for it to supply measures of degrees of belief, support, or plausibility (absolute or comparative). One of our central goals is to show how error probabilities can supply an inferential assessment of what can be learned from data. The second question leads to two philosophical conundrums: first how to explain when and why selection effects should alter the inferential assessment, and second, how to consider the relevant sample space without leading to the unique case, which would preclude error probabilities.

Controversy about these issues may be ameliorated with greater clarity on the roles in inference of calibration understood as error probabilities of methods. We describe our goal in [1] as follows:

Our goal is to identify a key principle of evidence by which hypothetical error probabilities may be used for inductive inference from specific data, and to consider how it may direct and justify (a) different uses and interpretations of statistical significance levels in testing a variety of distinct types of null hypotheses, and (b) when and why "selection effects" need to be taken account of in data dependent statistical testing. (78)

2. Statistical Significance Tests

Throughout our discussion, we discuss parallels between Fisher, Neyman and Pearson (N-P) and the philosopher Karl Popper, as well as between testing statistical and non-statistical hypotheses. If H is a statistical hypothesis, then usually no outcome strictly contradicts it. Nor would we want to regard data as inconsistent with H merely because they are highly improbable under H because “all individual outcomes described in detail may have very small probabilities. Rather, the issue, essentially following Popper (1959, 86, 203), is whether the possibly anomalous outcome represents some systematic and reproducible effect” ([1], 251). Here is where statistical significance tests enter. We begin “with the core elements of significance testing in a version very strongly related to but in some respect different from both Fisherian and Neyman-Pearson approaches...” (80). Statistical significance tests, as the statistician Allan Birnbaum aptly put it, are a small part of a rich set of “techniques for systematically appraising and bounding the probabilities (under respective hypotheses) of seriously misleading interpretations of data” (Birnbaum 1970, 1033). These are the method’s error probabilities and they are the basis for the calibration of frequentist or error statistical methods.

We have empirical data y viewed as observed values of a random variable Y whose probability distribution, defined by a statistical model, is regarded as an abstract and idealized representation of the underlying data-generating process. Data y are used to learn about the probability distribution of Y , by testing various statistical hypotheses. Neyman and Pearson called the main reference hypothesis the *test hypothesis*, while Fisher called it the *null hypothesis*, denoted by H_0 . A common null hypothesis H_0 , asserts that an experimental intervention has “no effect” or produces “no difference”.

The immediate objective is to test the conformity of the particular data under analysis with H_0 in some respect to be specified. To do this we find a function $t = t(y)$ of the data, to be called the *test statistic*, such that

- the larger the value of t the more inconsistent are the data with H_0 ;
- the corresponding random variable $T = t(Y)$ has a (numerically) known probability distribution when H_0 is true. ([1], 81)

These two requirements for test statistics are what enable statistical tests to serve the crucial roles of testing. In the interest of simplicity, unfortunately, popular expositions of statistical significance testing slide over them (Wasserstein and Lazar 2016). A test statistic is a special kind of statistic, and not just any “statistical summary of the data” can serve the role. The first requirement is that the test statistic actually track the hypothesis H_0 , generally given in terms of a value of a parameter. The larger the value of t , the more improbable the data under the assumption that H_0 adequately captures the relevant feature of the data generation. The second requirement is what enables computing the p-value corresponding to any value of t :

$$\text{p-value} = \Pr(T > t; H_0)$$

“regarded as a measure of concordance with H_0 in the respect tested” ([1], 81).⁴

In simple Fisherian tests, alternative hypotheses merely “lurk in the undergrowth” (81) whereas N-P tests explicitly formulate them. Our construal of tests applies to both. A p-value is the probability that the test would have given rise to a result more incompatible with H_0 than y is, were the results due to background or chance variability, as described in H_0 . It is a counterfactual claim. Small p-values (e.g., .05, .01, .005) indicate inconsistency with H_0 in the respect being probed by the test. But we can distinguish two main rationales: inductive behavior and inductive inference.

2.1 Inductive Behavior vs. Inductive Inference

The first rationale is the goal of following a rule with low error rates: “we may give any particular value p , say, the following hypothetical interpretation: suppose that we were to treat the data as just decisive evidence against H_0 . Then in hypothetical repetitions H_0 would be rejected in a long-run proportion p of the cases in which it is actually true” ([1], 81-82).

Cox views this as a behavioristic argument, in sync with Neyman and Pearson’s view of the aim of tests, namely, to avoid erroneous rejections (type 1 errors) and erroneous acceptances (type 2 errors) of hypotheses in the long-run of use.⁵ In the strict behavioristic construal often associated with Neyman, which Egon Pearson (1955) was not fond of, a rejection corresponds to taking some decision or action. It could be as inferential as declaring evidence of a discrepancy from H_0 , or as decision-theoretic as approving a drug. Although Cox often gives the low error-rate rationale in his discussion of tests, he avers that, at least in scientific contexts, this is solely to convey the meaning of terms in a testable or (“operational”) manner. It is not to be applied literally.

[T]here is a distinction between the Neyman–Pearson formulation of testing regarded as clarifying the meaning of statistical significance via hypothetical repetitions and that same theory regarded as in effect an instruction on how to implement the ideas by choosing a suitable α in advance and reaching different decisions accordingly. The interpretation to be attached to accepting or rejecting a hypothesis is strongly context-dependent . . . (Cox 2006, 36)

⁴ Insofar as one is interested in the direction of the effect, Cox thought it best to view two-sided tests as combining two one-sided tests, doubling the p-value for a selection effect (Cox and Hinkley, 1974, 79).

⁵ Neyman said “acceptance” was merely a shorthand: “My own preferred substitute for ‘do not reject H ’ is ‘no evidence against H is found’” (Neyman 1976, p. 749).

I call this Cox's "meaning vs. application" distinction (Mayo 2018). A main goal in [1] is to identify the relevance of error probabilities for an *inferential* interpretation.

2.2 Frequentist Principle of Evidence: FEV

As a starting point, we identified a general principle that we dubbed the Frequentist Principle of Evidence, **FEV**:

FEV(i): y is ... evidence against H_0 [or] evidence of discrepancy from H_0 , if and only if, [were H_0 adequate⁶] then, with high probability, this would have resulted in a less discordant result than is exemplified by y . ([1], 82)

The term "discrepancy" here refers to the parametric, not an observed, discordancy.

Statistical significance test reasoning reflects a straightforward conception of evaluating data purporting to supply evidence against H_0 when we know the observations are subject to variability and random fluctuation. Far from being the obscure technical analysis that some critics allege, it is akin to ordinary informal reasoning when we are keen to avoid being "fooled by randomness" (Benjamini 2016). If results even more incompatible with H_0 often occur due to chance variability alone—if the p-value is not small—then there are scarcely grounds to reject the chance explanation. In other words, the larger the p-value, the more *easily* our results can be generated by H_0 and thus the less evidence of a genuine discrepancy.

The reasoning may be regarded as a statistical version of the valid form of argument called in deductive logic *modus tollens*. This infers the denial of a hypothesis H from the combination that H entails E , together with the information that E is false. Because there was a high probability $(1 - p)$ that a less significant result would have occurred were H_0 true, we may justify taking low p -values, properly computed, as evidence against H_0 . ([1], 81)

Here "probability arises...to characterize the 'riskiness' or probativeness or severity of the tests to which hypotheses are put...reminiscent of the philosophy of Karl Popper" ([1], 82). In Popper's terms, if H_0 very probably would have "survived" the test (p-value not small), if true, and yet tests yield results discordant with H_0 , then there is an indication of the denial of H_0 . The stipulation that p-values be "properly computed" is all important. If, for example, data have been selectively reported to ensure a low nominal p-value, then the reasoning is illicit. I return to this in Section 3.

Of course, as Fisher always emphasized, we need "not an isolated record [of statistical significance] but a reliable method of proceeding" (1935a, 14). An analogy to which Cox often appeals is that of measuring devices:

The significance test is a measuring device for accordance with a specified hypothesis calibrated ...by its performance in repeated applications, ...we employ the performance features to make inferences about aspects of the particular thing that is measured, aspects that the measuring tool is appropriately capable of revealing. ([1], 84)

Error probabilities of tests indicate the capacity of the particular test to have revealed inconsistencies and discrepancies in the respects probed, and this in turn allows relating p-values to hypotheses about the process as statistically modelled.

2.3 We Need to Go Beyond Reporting the Observed P-value

⁶ The adequacy of H_0 means it is adequate as an approximate description of the data generating mechanism, in the manner of interest.

While **FEV** is set out in relation to a reference hypothesis H_0 , we would not stop with a single report of the attained p-value. Whether or not there is a predesignated p-value threshold, results are interpreted by considering several discrepancies from H_0 , and reporting how well or poorly tested they are with \mathbf{y} . The same reasoning in **FEV** is applied each time. This is where elements from N-P tests enter our formulation that began with the simple Fisherian test. Consider the context of what Cox calls *embedded hypotheses*. Here we have exhaustive parametric hypotheses governed by a parameter θ , such as the mean μ . A typical one-sided test is $H_0: \mu = \mu_0$ vs. $H_1: \mu > \mu_0$. To interpret evidence against a given H_0 , we apply **FEV** to several different hypotheses, each of form $\mu = \mu'$ where $\mu' = \mu_0 + d$. This enables determining if the data warrant inferring $\mu > \mu'$. Doing so gets around a weakness of p-values in failing to inform about the magnitude of discrepancies that are warranted. Our construal automatically blocks erroneously interpreting statistically significant results as indicating magnitudes of departures or discrepancies that are unwarranted.⁷

2.4 FEV (ii)

We need another principle in dealing with results that are statistically insignificant, or correspond to what Cox calls a “modest” or “moderate” p-value—namely one that is not small, say greater than .1. They are often imbued with two very different false interpretations: one is that (a) non-significance indicates the truth of the null, the other is that (b) non-significance is entirely uninformative.

The difficulty with regarding a modest value of p as evidence in favour of H_0 is that accordance between H_0 and \mathbf{y} may occur even if rivals to H_0 seriously different from H_0 are true. ... However, sometimes we can find evidence for ...an assertion that a particular discrepancy, flaw, or error is absent, and we can do this by means of tests that, with high probability, would have reported a discrepancy had one been present. ([1], 83)

We adapt **FEV(i)** in order to capture this reasoning in the one-sided example.

FEV(ii) : A moderate p value is evidence of the absence of a discrepancy δ from H_0 , only if there is a high probability the test would have given a worse fit with H_0 (i.e., smaller p value) were a discrepancy δ to exist. (83-4)

FEV(ii) is most apt in the case of embedded null hypotheses, as in testing $H_0: \mu = \mu_0$ vs. $H_1: \mu > \mu_0$.

[W]e may examine the probability $\beta(\delta)$ of observing a worse fit with H_0 if $\mu = \mu_0 + \delta$. If that probability is near one then, following **FEV(ii)**, the data are good evidence that $\mu < \mu_0 + \delta$. Thus $\beta(\delta)$ may be regarded as the stringency or severity with which the test has probed the discrepancy δ ...one might say that $\mu < \mu_0 + \delta$ has passed a severe test...[This] is more relevant to specific data than is the notion of power. (88-9)

A number of different terms can be introduced for the quantification associated with **FEV**.⁸

This interpretation of non-small p-values gets beyond classic fallacies of taking nonsignificant results as evidence for the null hypothesis. Some recent practitioners take fallacies of insignificance as grounds to either abandon significance, or restrict it to quality control decisions (behavioristic use) (Amrhein et al., 2019), but we need not abandon the tests to avoid such howlers. Cox has

⁷ We consider a number of different types of null hypotheses, each with corresponding alternatives. Even if the alternative is not explicit, the test statistic indicates the departures of interest. This enables the Fisherian to “do all N-P tests do (and more)” (Mayo 2018, 146).

⁸ Popper used “corroboration” and “severity” in his philosophical work but, unfortunately, he did not make use of modern statistics. I develop severe testing, both for general philosophy of science and in relation to shortcomings of statistical significance tests: Mayo (1996, 2018); Mayo and Spanos (2006, 2011); and Mayo and Hand (2022).

distinguished inferential from behavioristic uses of statistical significance tests in the over 60 years that he has written about them: Cox 1958 to Cox 2020.⁹

3. Selection effects

Selection effects may come in the form of multiple testing, data-dredging, optional stopping, p-hacking, and a number of other practices increasingly common with today's powerful computer techniques. These selection effects, not statistical significance tests, are responsible for the so-called replication crisis in science. Our discussion merges the disagreements about selection effects in philosophy of science and statistical science.

The general issue is whether the evidential bearing of data \mathbf{y} on an inference or hypothesis H_0 is altered when H_0 has been either constructed or selected for testing in such a way as to result in a specific observed relation between H_0 and \mathbf{y} , whether that is agreement or disagreement. Those who favour logical approaches to confirmation say no (e.g., Mill 1888, Keynes 1921), whereas those closer to an error statistical conception say yes (Whewell 1847, Pierce 1931-5). ([1], 91)

Error statistical considerations enable criteria to be identified for when selection effects matter and how to take account of the ways they alter relevant error probabilities. Whether the goal is behavioristic or evidential will also make a difference to any necessary adjustments. We examine six cases and apply **FEV** to consider whether allowance for selection is called for. For instance, if the null hypothesis H_0 is chosen for testing because the test statistic is large enough to reach a given level of statistical significance, the probability of finding some such discordance or other may be high, even under H_0 . The problem is not merely that 'fishing for significance' leads to poor error probabilities in the long run, it is that the test has done a poor job as a tool for discriminating genuine from chance effects in the case at hand. "Thus, following **FEV(i)**, we would not have genuine evidence of discordance with the null, and unless the p -value is modified appropriately, the inference would be misleading" ([1], 92). However, we should not run cases together simply because there is data dependence or multiple hypothesis testing.

Suppose we are testing for a DNA match with a known specimen, perhaps of a criminal, where it is given that probabilities of false negatives and false positives are very small. Unlike cases where the concern is inferring a genuine effect when in fact there is none, in cases like DNA matching there is a known effect, and it is given that reliable procedures are being used to identify the specific cause or source.

The probability is high that we would not obtain a match with person i , if i were not the criminal; so, by **FEV**, finding the match is ...good evidence that i is the criminal. Moreover, each nonmatch found, by the stipulations of the example, virtually excludes that person; thus, the more such negative results the stronger is the evidence when a match is finally found" ([1], 94).

⁹ Having extensively written on statistical significance tests and avoiding common pitfalls, Cox typically refrained from diving into the latest rounds of controversies surrounding them. However, he was sufficiently concerned with controversies erupting from the ASA Statement on p-values in 2016 (Wasserstein and Lazar 2016), the call to "redefine" statistical significance thresholds (to .005) in 2017 (Benjamin et al., 2017) and responses (Lakens et al. 2018), to encourage me to form a session at the 2018 RSS meeting (Cardiff), which he later joined ("Significance Tests: Rethinking the Controversy"). (Other speakers were Richard Morey and Aris Spanos.) His presentation became Cox (2020). His consternation grew much further with the 2019 call in Wasserstein et al., (2019) to "abandon statistical significance". He concurred with the ASA (President's) Task Force (Benjamini et al., 2021) that statistical significance tests "are important tools that should not be abandoned".

In broadly analogous cases, the warrant for the inferred explanation of the effect is improved by data dependent searching. Considerable discussion of selection effects, as with the other topics in our joint papers, may be found in Cox's work. Our goal was to use the principle we advance, **FEV**, to underwrite some of the distinctions Cox has made and positions he has taken elsewhere, on intuitive grounds.

4. Confidence Intervals

Confidence interval estimation is a frequentist method developed by Neyman (1934) as an "inversion" of statistical significance tests. Thus, it should also fall under our general frequentist principle of evidence. It does. In the example of one-sided testing of $\mu = \mu_0$ against $\mu > \mu_0$, a small p-value corresponds to μ_0 being (just) excluded from the corresponding $1 - p$ confidence interval (or $1 - 2p$ for the two-sided interval).

Were $\mu = \mu_L$, the lower confidence bound, then a less discordant result would occur with high probability ($1 - p$). Thus **FEV** licenses taking this as evidence of inconsistency with $\mu = \mu_L$ (in the positive direction). ([1], 90)

There are advantages to taking the testing construal as primary, as **FEV** does. For one thing, "this reasoning shows the advantage of considering several confidence intervals at a range of levels" (90). The idea of *confidence distributions* was first discussed in Cox's early 1958 paper. For a second, we can supply confidence intervals with an inferential as opposed to merely a behavioristic, coverage probability rationale. Third, our construal explains why Cox denies that statistical significance tests should be replaced by, or deemed subsidiary to, confidence intervals.

There are, however, powerful reasons for not taking sets of confidence intervals as the primary concept, essentially because of the possibility that nested sets of confidence or posterior intervals may not be the appropriate summary of information. ... the appropriate summary may be the outside of an interval or even the whole real line. In the latter case the confidence set is not a vacuous statement that the parameter is a real number, but rather a stark warning of the fragility of the data. (Cox 2020, 7)

The testing construal of confidence intervals, in sync with **FEV**, has the advantage of considering a confidence limit, interval or region as the set of parameter values that the data are not statistically significantly different than at a specified level "as assessed by testing each possible value in turn by some mutually concordant procedures" ([1], 91).

5. Objectivity and Conditionality in Frequentist Inference

I will now turn to a portion of our second joint paper, [2] "Objectivity and Conditionality in Frequentist Inference" (Cox & Mayo 2010). We consider a variety of types of conditioning discussed in Cox's work: conditioning for separation from nuisance parameters, conditioning to achieve uniformly most powerful rejection regions, and conditioning to induce relevance to the particular inference. It is regarding the last that we get to the second philosophical problem associated with the question of how we can ensure "that the hypothetical long run used in calibration is relevant to the specific data" without leading to the specific set of data, which would preclude error probabilities (Section 1.3). I focus on this. When Cox first proposed writing something jointly on conditionality, I hesitated because I was aware of a famous result in statistical foundations by Allan Birnbaum (1962) purporting to show that conditioning (for relevance) was in tension with frequentist error probabilities. As against this result, in [2] we argue that conditioning is warranted for frequentist theory to obtain the relevant sampling distribution.

We began with a notion of objectivity in statistics and in science more generally. It is a matter of both aims and methods.

Objective science, in our view, aims to find out what is the case as regards aspects of the world, independently of our beliefs, biases, and interests; thus objective methods aim for the critical control of inferences and hypotheses, constraining them by evidence and checks of error. ([2], 276)

We compare likelihoodist, Bayesian and frequentist methods in relation to objectivity, but here I will just be able to discuss the last.

Frequentist methods achieve an objective connection to hypotheses about the data-generating process by being constrained and calibrated by the method's error probabilities... ([2], 277)

5.1 Good Long-run Performance Is Not Enough

However, good long-run performance, while necessary for adequate inference, is not sufficient. Cox (1958) showed this with his famous example of two measuring instruments with different precisions. We flip a fair coin to test the mean of a Normal distribution using a test with either a very large, or very small, variance; and you know which was used.

Two measuring instruments of different precisions (“weighing machine” example): Suppose a single observation Y is made on a normally distributed random variable with unknown mean μ . A randomizing device chooses which of two instruments to use in measuring y : E' , or E'' , with [known] probabilities v' or v'' . The first instrument has known small variance, say 10^{-4} , whereas the second has known large variance, say 10^4 . ([2], 295)

He defines a “mixture test” where the randomizer, such as a fair coin toss, chooses the instrument, and then the p-value is calculated for testing a null hypothesis say, $\mu = 0$. The same y measurement corresponds to a much smaller p-value were it to have come from E' with its extremely small variance, than if it arose from E'' . The overall p-value from the mixture test would average over the two p-values. But it is given, as an essential part of the example, that you know which instrument was actually used. Intuitively, in that case, one ought to condition on the known instrument rather than report the p-value as the overall average, the *unconditional* p-value. Cox formulates the weak conditionality principle:

Weak Conditionality Principle (WCP): If a mixture experiment (of the aforementioned type) is performed, then if it is known which experiment produced the data, inferences about [parameter] θ are *appropriately drawn in terms of the sampling behavior in the experiment known to have been performed.* ([2], 296)

It is called weak conditionality because there are more general principles of conditioning that go beyond the special case of mixtures of measuring instruments.

5.2 Centrality of the “Weighing Machine” Example in Statistical Foundations

Although the WCP seems obvious, the “weighing machine” example is regarded as causing “a subtle earthquake” in statistical foundations. Why? There are two reasons. First, in Cox's example the best test on long-run optimality grounds is the unconditional test, which yields a misleading assessment of the p-value in the case at hand.

It would mean that an individual fortunate in obtaining the use of a precise instrument in effect sacrifices some of that information in order to rescue an investigator who has been unfortunate enough to have the randomizer choose a far less precise tool. From the perspective of interpreting the specific data that are actually available, this makes no sense. ([2], 296)

However, if one is in the context of acceptance sampling, where performance in a long-run series of applications is paramount, “the average performance may be the principal feature of interest, and

an unconditional approach suitable” (Lehmann and Romano 2005, 394). Scientific contexts, by contrast, call for identifying the appropriate sampling distribution for the inference at hand. In this case, that would be to condition on the tool known to have given rise to the data.

The second reason that Cox’s weighing machine example occupies a leading spot in statistical foundations is that it has been argued that conditioning for relevance, along the lines of the WCP, leads to the unique case. However, this would be tantamount to precluding error probabilities altogether, since they involve taking account of outcomes other than the one observed.

It is not uncommon to see statistics texts argue that in frequentist theory one is faced with the following dilemma: either to deny the appropriateness of conditioning on the precision of the tool chosen by the toss of a coin, or else to embrace the *strong likelihood principle*, which entails that frequentist sampling distributions are irrelevant to inference once the data are obtained. This is a false dilemma. Conditioning is warranted to achieve objective frequentist goals... The ‘dilemma’ argument is therefore an illusion. ([2], 298)

The argument that the weak conditionality principle (WCP) entails the strong likelihood principle (SLP)¹⁰, more commonly just called the likelihood principle (LP), is due to Allan Birnbaum (1962). Birnbaum regarded the ability of N-P tools to control the probability of misleading interpretations of data as the “one rock in a shifting scene” in statistical thinking and practice (Birnbaum 1970, 1033; see also Birnbaum 1977). So it is ironic that his own result seemed to lead to the LP, at least if one accepts the intuitively plausible WCP. (The Sufficiency Principle was not essential to his argument.) This precludes error probabilities.¹¹ Mayo (2014a) identifies a subtle, but fatal, logical fallacy in Birnbaum’s argument.¹²

6. Conclusion

The frequentist principles of evidence, **FEV (i)** and **(ii)**, are canonical pieces of statistical reasoning that need to be fleshed out in terms of questions and problems of inquiry requiring context-dependent background information. In each case, an inference is qualified by using error probabilities to determine not “how probable” but “how well probed” claims are, and what has been purely probed.

A fundamental tenet of the conception of inductive learning most at home with the frequentist philosophy is that inductive inference requires building up incisive arguments and inferences by putting together several different piece-meal results...Although the complexity of the issues makes it more difficult to set out neatly, as, for example, one could by imagining that a single algorithm encompasses the whole of inductive inference, the

¹⁰ For any two experiments E and E' with different probability models f, f' , but governed by the same unknown parameter θ , if outcomes x and y (from E and E' , respectively) determine the same likelihood function [$f(x;\theta) = cf'(y;\theta)$ for all θ], then x and y should lead to identical inferences concerning parameter θ .

¹¹ If inference is by Bayes theorem, we are led to the LP (Savage 1962, 17). Default or non-subjective Bayesians accept “technical violations” of the LP in order to match error probabilities, but the interpretation differs (Ghosh et al., 2006). “Frequentist error probabilities relate to the sampling distribution, where we consider hypothetically different outcomes that could have occurred in investigating this one system of interest. The Bayesian allusion to frequentist “matching” refers to the fixed data and considers frequencies over different systems (that could be investigated by a model like the one at hand)” ([2], 302).

¹² There is an extensive literature on this, see Mayo (2014a,b). A first look at the problem is sketched in an Appendix to the informal dialogue in Cox and Mayo 2011. Mayo 2014 a,b fills many gaps, and connects with other treatments. (A briefer version is Mayo 2013.) For the continued controversy, see the six discussion of Mayo 2014a by A.P. Dawid, M. Evans, R. Martin & C. Liu, D.A.S. Fraser, J. Hannig, and J. Bjornstad.

payoff is an account that approaches the kind of arguments that scientists build up in order to obtain reliable knowledge and understanding of a field. ([1], 96)

Our discussions in [1] and [2] take up other foundational issues and principles that Cox has advanced over many years: relating statistical and scientific inference, testing the assumptions of models, and comparing rival paradigms for interpreting probability, frequentist and Bayesian.¹³ They still only cover a small set of the tremendous foundational contributions that Cox has advanced with far greater statistical sophistication and depth. Our goal was to synthesize some of his foundational ideas to address the open philosophical, conceptual, and logical questions given in the opening of this paper. Scientists will find a wealth of seminal ideas and illumination in Cox's work.¹⁴ We have much to learn from him.

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¹³ Section 11 of [2] gives an overview of Bayesian alternatives. Appendix B of Cox 2006 gives “a personal view”. An analysis of [1] and [2] is Spanos (2010).

¹⁴ Nancy Reid, inaugural winner of the David R. Cox Foundations of Statistics award, spoke on “The Importance of Foundations” at the JSM 2023.

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